

Implementation of Strategic Management in Building Student Character in Education Institutions in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this research is to find out and analyze strategic management in realizing student character how student character is manifested and what are the obstacles and solutions in realizing student character. The research method used in this research is a qualitative method with the main data source being observation and interviews with informants who have been selected in this research. The informants in this research were the school principal, teachers, school committee, and students' parents. The analysis technique in this research uses the Miles and Huberman analysis model. The results of the research show that strategy management realizes student characteristics, namely, strategy formulation, strategy implementation, and strategy evaluation. Students' character can be categorized as good, such as good manners, independence, self-confidence, discipline, maintaining cleanliness, dressing neatly, being obedient, and having respect for other people. The challenge in developing student character is including the social environment outside the madrasah. Therefore, it is necessary to have the maximum involvement of parents in preventing deviant behavior.

KEYWORDS: Strategy Formulation, Strategy Implementation, Strategy Evaluation, Student Character

INTRODUCTION

Strategic management is a system as a single unit, having various interconnected components, that influence each other, and move simultaneously in the same direction. Strategic management is the highest management activity which is usually arranged by the Chief Executive Officer (CEO) and the organization's executive team. Strategic management provides overall direction for an organization and is closely related to organizational behavior. Strategic management talks about the big picture, and the core and identifies organizational goals, resources, and how existing resources can be used effectively to meet strategic goals (Medina & Medina, 2017). Likewise, strategic management discusses the relationship between an organization and its environment, both the internal environment and the external environment (Menguc et al., 2010; Sarbah & Otu-Nyarko, 2014). Therefore, the strategic management of Islamic educational institutions at this time must provide a basic foundation/guideline for decision-making in the management of educational institutions and the importance of this management determines the quality to be achieved. Not only for Islamic educational institutions but also for the world of education in general. Because education is a basic right of every citizen without exception. Efforts to improve the quality of education in this country have long been pursued. Since Indonesia's independence until the current era of reform. Improving the quality of education is one of the development priorities in the education sector. Various innovations and educational programs have also been implemented. Completion of the curriculum, procurement of teaching materials, procurement of infrastructure, and including improving the quality of teachers.

This effort was carried out with the hope of giving birth to the complete Indonesian people, as stated in the applicable legislation. Quality education must be provided through the channels, types, and levels that exist in our education system, including Islamic higher education, madrasahs, and Islamic boarding schools. The role of education is directed at achieving national development through approaches to religious, psychological, economic, cultural aspects, and of course scientific aspects. The National Education System Law Number 20 of 2003 mandates that national education functions to develop abilities and form character, as well as a dignified national civilization, to make the nation's life more intelligent, aimed at developing the potential of students to become human beings who believe in and are devoted to God Almighty, with good morals. noble, healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and a democratic and responsible citizen. This role must be attached to every pathway, type, and level of education contained in the education administration regulations.

Based on the goals of national education, education is not only related to efforts to master the academic field by students but must be balanced with character formation. The balance of academic education and character formation needs to be considered in the management of educational institutions (Ginanjar, 2017). If this balance is carried out, then education can become the basis for turning children into better-quality people in terms of faith, knowledge, and morals. Education is not only related to increasing knowledge but must include aspects of attitudes and behavior so that it can make children into human beings who are devout, knowledgeable, and have noble character. The idea of a character education program in Indonesia emerged in connection with national education goals and seeing the condition of students who are currently experiencing character degradation. Character is something good, for example, related to honesty, tolerance, hard work, fairness, trustworthiness, etc (Anasri, 2019; Sani & Kadri, 2016). However, without a strong faith in Allah SWT, this character may go beyond the boundaries of Islamic teachings.

The Director General of Islamic Religious Education, Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia, stated that character can be interpreted as the totality of personal characteristics that are inherent and can be identified in individual behavior that is unique, in the sense that these characteristics specifically differentiate one individual from another (E. Mulyasa, 2013, p. 4). Because these character traits can be identified in unique individual behavior, the character is very close to the individual's personality. Even though the character of each individual is unique, general characteristics become stereotypes of a group of people and nations, which can be identified as the character of a particular community or can even be seen as the character of a nation. Based on research at Harvard University in the United States, it turns out that a person's success is not determined solely by knowledge and technical abilities (hard skills), but rather by the ability to manage oneself and others (soft skills). This research reveals that success is only determined around 20 percent by hard skills and the remaining 80 percent by soft skills (Wiyani, 2018, p. 12).

This suggests that soft skills are part of the character that must be formed through Early Childhood Education at University. Unfortunately, nowadays, due to the enormity of globalization as an illogical consequence of the incessant flow of information between countries through information media and sophisticated technology, there is a war of ideas and the hegemony of one culture over another culture, bringing the values it promotes that defeat the previous noble values, especially religious values. For example, brawls between students, drug abuse, sexual harassment, promiscuity, domestic violence, corruption, fraud, and various other deviant behavior. Likewise, there are many accusations regarding the role played by educational institutions. Education is considered to have failed in forming the next generation. The indication is that behavior/characters, profiles, and educational products are far from national education targets. Even though education has given birth to a generation with several competencies. To maintain this, external support is needed in the form of information and media systems, economic access, and cultural values that develop in society. So it is irrational if education is accused of being the cause of failure. Therefore, to prevent abusive behavior, efforts are needed to build the character of students in educational institutions. Whyne argued that character comes from the Greek word which means "to mark" (mark) and focuses on how to apply good values in one's obedient actions or daily behavior. Therefore, someone who behaves dishonestly, cheating, cruel, and greedy is said to have bad character, while someone who behaves well, honestly, and likes to help is said to have good/noble character (E. Mulyasa, 2013, p. 5).

Madrasah Aliyah Negeri (MAN) in Watampone City, which consists of MAN 1 and MAN 2, has achievements including academic and non-academic, adequate facility readiness, human resource readiness, and various student services. This can be realized because of the management of madrasah heads who are oriented towards improving the quality of education. Public interest has also increased from year to year. On average, it can be said that the character of students at MAN 1 Bone is good, but there are still students whose politeness and discipline still need to be improved. Based on the description above, the author will research Strategic Management in Realizing the Character of Students (Study of State Islamic Madrasahs in Watampone City, Indonesia).

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Strategy Management

Strategic management is a process/series of fundamental and comprehensive decision-making activities, accompanied by determining how to implement them, which are made by the leadership and implemented by all levels in the organization, to achieve goals. According to J. David Hunger and Thomas Weelen, strategic management is a series of managerial decisions and actions that determine long-term company performance (Thomas L. Wheleen and J. David Hunger, 2010). Strategic management includes environmental observation, strategy formulation (strategic planning/long-term planning), strategy implementation, and evaluation and control. According to Hadari Nawawi, strategic management is a process or series of decision-making activities that are

fundamental and comprehensive and accompanied by determining how to carry them out, which are made by top management and implemented by all levels within an organization to achieve its goals (Nawawi, 2012).

The principle in strategic management is a strategy formulation that reflects the true desires and goals of the organization, there is an implementation strategy that describes how to achieve the goal (technically). Implementation strategies reflect organizational capabilities and allocations, including performance-based financial allocations, as well as evaluation strategies that can measure, evaluate, and provide feedback on organizational performance (Aulia et al., 2023). The stages of strategic management are strategy formulation, implementation, and evaluation (Wheelen et al., 2017). Strategy formulation is determining the program or plan that an organization will implement to achieve the final goals it wants to achieve as well as the events that will be used to achieve these goals (Padash & Ghatari, 2020; Simons, 2019). Strategy formulation includes developing a vision, and mission, identifying external opportunities and threats for an organization, awareness of internal strengths and weaknesses, setting long-term goals, searching for alternative strategies, and selecting certain strategies to achieve goals. The next stage is implementing the strategy. Implementing a strategy requires setting annual goals, creating policies, motivating employees, and allocating resources so that each strategy that has been formulated can be implemented (Kabeyi, 2019). Strategy implementation includes developing a culture that is supportive of the strategy, creating an effective organizational structure, redeploying marketing efforts, preparing budgets, developing and utilizing information systems, and linking employee compensation to organizational performance. Strategy implementation is often called the action and strategy management stages. Implementing a strategy means mobilizing employees and managers to implement the strategy that has been formulated. Often considered a difficult stage in strategic management, strategy implementation requires discipline, commitment, and personal sacrifice. Successful strategy implementation depends on the manager's ability to motivate employees, which is more of an art than a science. The strategies that have been formulated are useful if implemented. Strategy assessment is the final stage in strategic management (Shujahat et al., 2017). The main focus in strategy evaluation is performance measurement and creating an effective feedback mechanism. Performance measurement is an important stage to see and evaluate the achievements or results of work that has been carried out by the organization to achieve predetermined targets.

2. Character Education

Students are anyone who is registered as a student object at an educational institution (Suharismi Arikunto, 2005). According to the National Education System Law, students are members of society who seek to develop their potential through the learning processes available at certain pathways, levels and types of education. Thus, a student is someone who is registered in a particular pathway, level and type of educational institution who always wants to develop his or her potential both in academic and non-academic aspects through the learning process that is carried out.

According to the Big Indonesian Dictionary, character is the psychological traits, morals, or manners that differentiate a person from others. Character can also be interpreted as the basic values that build a person's personality which are influenced by heredity and the environment, which differentiate him from other people, and are manifested in his attitudes and behavior in everyday life (Akdon, 2006, p. 82). Whyne argued that character comes from Greek which means "to mark" and focuses on how to apply good values in real actions or daily behavior. Therefore, a person who behaves dishonestly, cheats, is cruel and greedy is said to be a person who has bad character, while someone who behaves well, is honest, and likes to help is said to be a person who has a good/noble character (E. Mulyasa, 2013, p. 5). Lickona further emphasized the importance of three components of good character, namely moral knowing or knowledge about morals, moral feeling or feelings about morals, and moral action or moral actions.

Moral knowing is related to moral awareness, knowing moral values, perspective-taking, moral reasoning, decision-making, and self-knowledge. Moral feelings are related to conscience, self-esteem, empathy, loving the good, self-control, and humility; while moral action is a combination of moral knowing and moral feeling which is manifested in the form of competence, desire, and habit. These three components need to be considered in character education, so that students realize, understand, feel, and can pay attention to the virtues in their daily lives completely and comprehensively (kaffah). Megawangi, the founder of character education in Indonesia, has compiled 9 pillars of character that can be used as a reference in character education, both at school and outside school, namely as follows;

1. Love of Allah and truth
2. Responsibility, discipline, and independence
3. Trustworthy

4. Respectful and polite
5. Affection, care, and cooperation
6. Confident, creative, and never give up
7. Fair and have a leadership spirit
8. Kind and humble
9. Tolerance and love of peace (E. Mulyasa, 2013, p. 5)

About the development of character values, the Grand Design Draft for character education reveals the main values developed in the culture of formal and non-formal education units as follows:

1. Be honest
2. Be responsible
3. Smart
4. Healthy and clean, respects order, regularity, discipline, skilled, protects the environment, implements a balanced lifestyle
5. Caring
6. Creative
7. Cooperation (Suhra, 2016)

According to Didin Nantara in (Musbikin, 2021) :

- a. Character education is an effort to instill behavioral values in students to become children who have noble, moral, ethical, cultured, and civilized behavior based on religion and Pancasila. Schools not only form students who excel academically but also form students who have good attitudes and behavior.
- b. The formation of student character through activities at school can be carried out through various routine and spontaneous activities to shape children into positive or good behavioral values. Examples of student characters that can be formed through routine and spontaneous activities include nationalism, social care, discipline, environmental care, curiosity, and religiousness.
- c. The formation of student character through the role of the teacher can be done through learning activities and examples. Through learning activities, examples of student character that are formed include honesty and cooperation.
- d. Meanwhile, through the teacher's example, the teacher's good behavior or personality will be imitated or imitated by students with good behavior.

From an Islamic perspective, theoretical character education has existed since Islam was revealed to the world; along with the sending of the Prophet Muhammad seen to improve or perfect human morals (character) (Sirait, 2022). Islamic teachings themselves contain systematic teachings that not only emphasize aspects of faith, worship, and mu'amalah, but also morals. The complete practice of Islamic religious teachings (kaffah) is a model of the character of a Muslim, even personified by the character model of the Prophet Muhammad, who has the characteristics of Shidiq, Tabligh, Amanah, Fathanah (Pujawardani, 2019). Children are a trust entrusted to us by Allah SWT to be cared for and educated to become God-fearing human beings. Children can be helpers for us in the afterlife. However, children will also be an obstacle for us to enter heaven if we are not educated well. Efforts to become a heartbreaker are not easy because several challenges will be faced, especially from the surrounding environment. One of the things that needs to be done is to set an example in implementing the Al-Quran and Sunnah in everyday life, as well as training children to become a generation that has noble morals by the guidance of the Koran and the Sunnah of the Prophet (Manan, 2017).

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is qualitative. Therefore, research creativity makes a major contribution to the quality of research results. In terms of its objectives, qualitative research aims to find interactive relationships, discover theories, describe complex realities, and gain an understanding of meaning, so it can be understood that qualitative research will produce a new theory or reinterpretation of previous research. State Aliyah Madrasah in Watampone City. Consists of two madrasahs, namely MAN 1 and MAN 2 in Bone Regency. Primary data in this research is data obtained from primary sources, either through interviews, documentation, or observation. Interviews with madrasah principals, deputy madrasah principals, teaching staff and educational staff, students, and the community. Secondary data in this research are documents related to research objects that are available in various forms in the form of evidence, notes, or historical reports that have been compiled in published and unpublished archives (documentary data). This data was obtained from institutions, companies, or parties related to this research. Data collection in this research was carried out using

Observation, Interview, and Documentation techniques. In qualitative research, data obtained through interviews, observations, documentation, and other records are still raw data and tend to be unsystematic. Therefore, data processing and analysis are required. In this research, data processing and analysis follow the qualitative analysis pattern pioneered by Miles and Huberman, namely reduction, display, and conclusion or verification.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Strategic management is a series of activities for fundamental and comprehensive decision-making, accompanied by leadership determining how to apply them, which are carried out by all parties involved in a company in achieving the expected goals. Strategic management is a system that is used as a unit that has various components that are interconnected influence one another and move simultaneously in the same direction (Jacobides et al., 2018). Therefore, in realizing student character at MAN Watampone City, strategic management includes strategy formulation, strategy implementation, and strategy evaluation. Strategic planning for developing student character is carried out by conducting internal and external analysis (Iskandar et al., 2022). Based on the results of the interviews that have been conducted, it can be understood that environmental analysis is carried out together with madrasa stakeholders so that weaknesses, strengths, challenges, and opportunities can be identified, making it easier to formulate student character development programs.

The strategy formulation at MAN Watampone City includes planning that refers to and aims at achieving the Madrasah Vision. A vision is an ideal condition that will be realized within a certain period and becomes a guide and direction in managing the madrasah. Based on the interviews that have been conducted, it can be understood that MAN's vision in Watampone City includes the development of student character, namely religious, noble, and trustworthy. The formulation of this vision involves madrasah stakeholders, namely the deputy head of the madrasa, teachers, education staff, community/committee, and supervisors. Based on observations at MAN 1 Bone and MAN 2 Bone, it is clear that the vision of the state madrasah (MAN 1 Bone and MAN 2 Bone) is displayed in the Madrasah so that it can be seen at all times by madrasah residents. Judging from the madrasah, it can be understood that MAN in Watampone City has a strategic step, namely the mission of realizing the vision of the madrasah and visible efforts to develop the character of students to create students who excel in both academic and non-academic fields. The vision and mission are well socialized, as stated by the two heads of madrasahs, The vision and mission of the madrasah are socialized in new student admissions activities, meetings with madrasah residents and committees, flag ceremonies, student activities, banners, brochures, social media, and others. The aims and objectives of this socialization are that externally the madrasah is recognized by the community and internally to build commitment and awareness of all madrasah residents so that their thoughts and actions are directed towards achieving the vision and mission of the madrasah.

Based on the results of interviews, observations, and documentation that have been carried out, it can be understood that MAN in Watampone City has a clear vision and mission and is also oriented towards developing student character. The formulation of the vision and mission involves madrasa stakeholders and socialists in various activities so that they are understood by interested parties. Vision is a series of words that contain dreams, ideals, values, and the future of an organization, both within an institution and a company. Vision is also an organization's goal in working. The vision is created from the thoughts of the founders regarding the future image of the organization. Vision can have the function of determining future steps, inspiring members, and motivating members to make maximum contributions. Therefore, the series of words used in a vision must be concise and clear, generally only one sentence or no more than one paragraph. Vision will be very influential when the organization wants to make changes.

The vision keeps the organization running according to what the founder aspired to so that the vision will prevent an organization from forming a new direction or deviating from the vision's goals (Lashway, 1997). The creation of a vision plays a very important role in taking the next steps, a vision cannot stand alone. Therefore, the vision or picture of the future needs an explanation regarding how to plan to move forward. That's where the role of mission comes into play. The mission will also answer several questions such as how the madrasah behaves, how to try to succeed, and how to measure a progress process. So, a mission can be summed up as a set of plans or methods determined to realize a predetermined vision. The language of the vision and mission should support each other, but the mission statement is more specific than the vision. The mission will determine the characteristics of the organization compared to other organizations. What is conveyed in the mission can usually include products or services that will be prioritized. This is what makes the mission set in the vision and at the same time describes the plan for making an action so that the character of the students is realized.

Before establishing a student character development program, what must be done is an analysis of the internal and external environment so that madrasa planning is right on target. Planning is the initial action before carrying out activities in an organization. This planning is a determinant of differences in the performance of one organization with another organization. It's actually planning providing direction, reducing influence, change, growth, donations and compiling measurements to facilitate supervision. Planning is the activity of thinking about and selecting a series of actions aimed at achieving educational aims and objectives. 40 Planning is "the process of setting objectives and determining what should be done to accomplishment (the process of setting goals and what should be done to achieve these goals)." 41 Planning on Basically, it is a process of determining activities that will be carried out in the future. This activity aims to organize various resources so that the results achieved are as expected. This means that in the planning process there are efforts to use human resources, natural resources and other resources to achieve goals. According to Roger A. Kauffman, planning is the process of determining the goals or targets to be achieved or targets to be achieved and determining the paths and resources needed to achieve the goals effectively and efficiently.

From the results of the interviews that have been conducted, it can be understood that all parties participated in the planning and development of the program to realize student character. Improvements are made to all components that influence students, including aspects of the curriculum, infrastructure, human resources (teachers, education staff, parents/community), school culture, student programs or activities, and the community environment. Before establishing a student character development program, what must be done is an analysis of the internal and external environment so that madrasa planning is right on target. Planning is the initial action before carrying out activities in an organization. This planning is a determinant of differences in the performance of one organization with another organization. Planning provides direction, reduces influence, changes, growth, and contributions, and develops measures to facilitate supervision.

Planning is the activity of thinking about and choosing a series of actions aimed at achieving educational aims and objectives (Ilyasin & Nurhayati, 2012, p. 127). Planning is "the process of setting objectives and determining what should be done to accomplish (Mulyono, 2008, p. 24)." Planning is the process of determining activities that will be carried out in the future. This activity aims to organize various resources so that the results achieved are as expected. This means that in the planning process, there are efforts to use human resources, natural resources, and other resources to achieve goals. According to Roger A. Kauffman, planning is the process of determining the goals or targets to be achieved or targets to be achieved and determining the paths and resources needed to achieve the goals effectively and efficiently (Kaufman, 1972). Bateman and Snell suggest that planning is determining the goals that must be achieved and deciding on the priority actions needed to achieve these goals (Bateman & Snell, 2019). Koontz presents planning as an intellectual process that consciously determines the actions to be taken and bases decisions on the goals to be achieved, timely and reliable information, and paying attention to estimates of future conditions (Engkoswara & Komariah, 2010, p. 132). So it can be concluded that planning is the process of determining activities to be carried out within a certain period by utilizing existing resources to achieve the expected goals.

Strategy implementation includes developing a culture that is supportive of the strategy, creating an effective organizational structure, redeploing marketing efforts, preparing budgets, developing and utilizing information systems, and linking employee compensation to organizational performance. Based on the results of interviews that have been conducted, it can be seen that in building student character, the things that are done are, for example, habituation, guidance, training, giving advice, advice, collaboration with parents of students through committees, and sanctions. Other things that can create student character are building a madrasa culture such as exemplary, mutual respect, discipline, maintaining cleanliness, activating extracurricular organizational activities, religious culture, child-friendly, habituation, exemplary, cooperation with related parties, educational punishment, politeness, giving advice, motivation. , the culture of appreciation, entrepreneurship programs, and assisting disaster victims.

Based on researchers' observations, various MAN activities can be seen in Watampone City, Indoensia such as student development, market day activities, exhibitions, Dhuh prayers, Dhuhur prayers, religious commemoration activities, group Koran reading, and smiles, greetings, and greetings. So based on the results of interviews and observations, it can be seen that MAN in Watampone City actively develops student character, both personal, social, and religious character, and always collaborates in this development as well as the motivation and enthusiasm of madrasah leaders so that the implementation of the character development program is carried out smoothly. The next step in character building is resource empowerment. Based on the results of interviews, observations, and documentation, it can be understood that efforts to develop the character of MAN students in Watampone City are supported by a clear division of tasks and functions, division of tasks adjusted to education, talents and interests, empowerment of infrastructure

and cooperation of all parties. This is related to the implementation of the education management function, namely organizing. The organizing function is intended to combine all existing resources in the organization, both human resources and other resources towards achieving educational goals. Through the organization, all educational resources, both human and material, are arranged and combined in such a way that educational goals can be achieved effectively and efficiently. Organizing refers more to the process of organization, namely the activity of preparing or allocating work, people, and objects so that they can be used to achieve organizational goals.

In any school, Human Resources (HR) occupies the most vital position. It is acknowledged that cost is important. Likewise facilities, infrastructure, and technology. However, the availability of these resources is wasted if they are handled by people who are incompetent and lack commitment. Efforts to plan the needs of teaching and education personnel (HR), and organize, select, place, and give assignments appropriately have become important concerns in every competitive school. Likewise, compensation policies (salaries and welfare) and performance assessments that are carried out fairly and precisely can create achievement motivation in teaching and education staff. Such human resource management functions are still not enough if they are not accompanied by policies for the development and empowerment of teaching and educational staff which are carried out systematically.

Strategy assessment is the final stage in strategic management. The main focus in Strategy Evaluation is performance measurement and creating effective feedback mechanisms. Performance measurement is an important stage to see and evaluate the achievements or results of work that has been carried out by the organization to achieve predetermined targets. Based on the results of the interview, it can be understood that evaluating the character development of MAN students in Watampone City is carried out at any time both during the learning process and outside the classroom. Monitoring and evaluation is carried out by all parties using various techniques and approaches and evaluation is carried out continuously both in the learning process and outside the classroom, and is carried out during meetings with the teacher council including grade promotion meetings. The purpose of evaluation and the function of evaluation, evaluation is an identification process to measure/assess whether an activity or program is implemented by the plan or objectives to be achieved. Some say that the meaning of evaluation is an activity to collect information about the performance of something (methods, people, equipment), where this information will be used to determine the best alternative in making decisions. Evaluation is needed in various areas of human life to increase effectiveness and productivity, both in the individual, group, and work environment. Evaluation is not carried out without a purpose, but there are things to be achieved through this activity.

Character can be interpreted as the basic values that build a person's personality which are influenced by heredity and environment, which differentiate him from other people, and are manifested in his attitudes and behavior in everyday life. Strategic management is applied in realizing the character of \ students in Watampone City, Indonesia, including being honest, responsible, intelligent, healthy and clean, caring, creative and cooperative. Based on the results of interviews and observations in the city of Watampone, that: The students' character is good, such as good manners, independence, self-confidence, discipline, maintaining cleanliness, neat dressing, obedient, highlighting the "Tabe" culture, high motivation in following activity. Thus, it can be seen that character development strategies with ongoing programs and evaluations can improve the character of students in Watampone City. So that the Madrasah is increasingly in demand by the public.

The challenge in developing student character is including the social environment outside the madrasah. Therefore, it is necessary to maximize the involvement of students' parents in preventing deviant behavior. Based on Heri Gunawan's theory in his book which says that humans always live in contact with other humans or also with the natural surroundings. That is the reason why humans have to socialize and in this interaction influence each other's thoughts, traits and behavior. So if you want the internalization of religious character values to be well internalized, healthy environmental conditioning must be carefully considered in an environment that supports character formation, so at least it will be influenced by that environment. In relationships, of course we have to look carefully at which relationships provide benefits. Because this character will certainly turn into a bad character if the people around us don't support it. Based on the results of the interview, it can be understood that the challenges in developing student character come from the students themselves, such as discipline that still needs to be improved and challenges from the external or social environment.

CONCLUSION

Strategy Management in realizing MAN student performance in Watampone City, namely, strategy formulation, strategy implementation, and strategy evaluation. The character of MAN students in Watampone City consists of honesty, Responsible,

Smart, health, and clean, respect for order, regularity, discipline, skilled, protection of the environment, implementing a balanced lifestyle, caring, creativity, and cooperation. Obstacles and solutions in realizing the character of MAN students in Watampone City. Internal challenges for students are a discipline that still needs to be improved and challenges from the external environment or relationships. Character can be interpreted as the basic values that build a person's personality which are influenced by heredity and environment, which differentiate him from other people, and are manifested in his attitudes and behavior in everyday life. Based on the results of this research, it can be seen that guidance from teachers in both academic and extracurricular activities has an impact on the honesty of MAN students in Watampone City. The value of honesty is applied both inside and outside the madrasah. Therefore, the caring attitude of educational institutions in realizing student character is always the main concern, and synergy between the community and the government continues to be established.

REFERENCES

1. Anasri, A. (2019). Membentuk karakter dengan Al-Qur'an, satu perspektif pendidikan islam. *Al-Fikra: Jurnal Ilmiah Keislaman*, 17(2), 218–248.
2. Aulia, D., Soleh, M., & Hariyati, N. (2023). Manajemen Strategik Pengelolaan Sekolah Di Mi Tri Shakti Surabaya. *Jurnal Ilmiah Mandala Education*, 9(1).
3. Bateman, T., & Snell, S. (2019). *Management: Leading & Collaborating in Competitive World*, 13e.
4. E. Mulyasa. (2013). *Manajemen Pendidikan Karakter*. Bumi Aksara.
5. Engkoswara, A. K., & Komariah, A. (2010). Administrasi pendidikan. *Bandung: Alfabeta*.
6. Ginanjar, M. H. (2017). Keseimbangan peran orang tua dalam pembentukan karakter anak. *Edukasi Islami: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam*, 2(03).
7. Ilyasin, M., & Nurhayati, N. (2012). *Manajemen pendidikan Islam: Konstruksi teoritis dan praktis*. Aditya Media Pub.
8. Iskandar, A., Rusydi, I., Amin, H., Hakim, M. N., & Haqq, H. A. (2022). Strategic Management in Improving the Quality of Education in Boarding School. *AL-ISHLAH: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 14(4), 7229–7238.
9. Jacobides, M. G., Cennamo, C., & Gawer, A. (2018). Towards a theory of ecosystems. *Strategic Management Journal*, 39(8), 2255–2276.
10. Kabeyi, M. (2019). Organizational strategic planning, implementation and evaluation with analysis of challenges and benefits. *International Journal of Applied Research and Studies*, 5(6), 27–32.
11. Kaufman, R. A. (1972). *Educational system planning*.
12. Lashway, L. (1997). *Leading with Vision*. ERIC.
13. Manan, S. (2017). Pembinaan akhlak mulia melalui keteladanan dan pembiasaan. *Jurnal Pendidikan Agama Islam-Ta'lim*, 15(1), 49–65.
14. Medina, R., & Medina, A. (2017). Managing competence and learning in knowledge-intensive, project-intensive organizations: A case study of a public organization. *International Journal of Managing Projects in Business*, 10(3), 505–526.
15. Menguc, B., Auh, S., & Ozanne, L. (2010). The interactive effect of internal and external factors on a proactive environmental strategy and its influence on a firm's performance. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 94, 279–298.
16. Mulyono, M. A. (2008). *Manajemen Administrasi dan Organisasi Pendidikan*. Ar-Ruzz Media, Yogyakarta.
17. Musbikin, I. (2021). *Pendidikan Karakter Jujur*. Nusamedia.
18. Nawawi, H. (2012). *Manajemen Strategik Organisasi Non Profit Bidang Pemerintah: Yogyakarta*. Gadjah Mada University Press.
19. Padash, A., & Ghatari, A. R. (2020). Toward an Innovative Green Strategic Formulation Methodology: Empowerment of corporate social, health, safety and environment. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 261, 121075.
20. Pujawardani, H. H. (2019). Pendidikan Karakter Melalui Internalisasi Nilai-Nilai Agama Islam Pada Anak Usia Dini. *Media Nusantara*, 16(1), 77–90.
21. Sani, R. A., & Kadri, M. (2016). *Pendidikan Karakter: Mengembangkan Karakter Anak yang Islami*. Bumi Aksara.
22. Sarbah, A., & Otu-Nyarko, D. (2014). An overview of the design school of strategic management (strategy formulation as a process of conception). *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 2014.

23. Simons, R. (2019). The role of management control systems in creating competitive advantage: new perspectives. In *Management Control Theory* (pp. 173–194). Routledge.
24. Sirait, I. (2022). Pendidikan Karakter Dalam Pendidikan Islam. *PENDALAS: Jurnal Penelitian Tindakan Kelas Dan Pengabdian Masyarakat*, 2(2), 82–88.
25. Suharismi Arikunto. (2005). *Manajemen Penelitian*. Adi Mhasatya.
26. Thomas L. Wheleen and J. David Hunger. (2010). *Strategic Management and Business Policy Achieving Sustainability International Edition* (E. Svendsen (ed.); Internatio). Prentice Hall.
27. Wheelen, T. L., Hunger, J. D., Hoffman, A. N., & Bamford, C. E. (2017). *Strategic management and business policy* (Vol. 55). pearson Boston.
28. Wiyani, N. A. (2018). Pendidikan karakter berbasis total quality management: konsep dan aplikasi di sekolah. (*No Title*).